

A bibliography of Russian disinformation operations

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Note

This is a list of sources that may be consulted on Russian disinformation operations since 2014. The list is not meant to be exhaustive, but should provide ample information for anyone interested in the subject matter. These sources cover issues such as the Internet Research Agency, Russian involvement in US, European and South African elections, vaccines, COVID-19 and the war in Ukraine.

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